

STRESS MANAGEMENT AMONG GRADUATES

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Abstract:

Stress has become an inevitable part of lives. Stress arises as a result of relations with the constantly changing environment and the adaptation to it. Actually managing stress is an art, through this all human beings can enjoy their life in its full spirit. Stress management is the need of the hour. Stressors, if not escapable, are fairly manageable. College students are at a critical period where they will enter adulthood. They are expected to be the elites in the society. Thus, they should enhance their stress management abilities so as to live a healthy life after entering the society. The life stress on them is considerable. Therefore, understanding the sources of stress among them and how they can cope with the stress is very important. This study focused on 295 college students of Pollachi Taluk to explore their stress sources and coping strategies through a questionnaire survey. The main aim of this study was to find out the level of stress among graduates. The stress level is measured with the help of a structured questionnaire. Perceived Stress Scale and Depression, Anxiety Stress Scales were used to measure the stress level. The total score of stress level comes around 72. The overall average stress index is 65.16. Statistical tools namely ANOVA and Chi-square have been administered. The result of the study reveals that a good and proper guidance should be followed by the students. Some factors from the family, educational institutions and the society influence the students a lot. In order to overcome all the barriers which are against to the development of the students should identify and proper measures should be taken. A co-operative attempt by the parents, teachers, educational institutions and from the government should be there to create a stress free generation in future. Stress free creates pleasant environment such as mental peace, better and healthy thoughts, good relations, service motives and indirectly it avoids social, economic and political unrest. It leads to acquire more knowledge to fulfil their future dreams.

Key Words: Stress Level Index, Graduates & Stress Management Techniques

1. Introduction:

Everyone in today's fast paced world is plagued by stress every day. The means of tackling stress are differ from person to person. The need of the day is to help people successfully to combat stress. Facing stress is unavoidable, but effectively tackling it is a necessity. A group of people who are most frequently affected by stress are students. Throughout their academic lives, students face various challenges and a whole lot of pressure in today's competitive environment. Students need to be trained in handling stress. Handling stress is an art by itself and it needs some proven scientific methods to manage it. Several demands are placed during the life of a student. These demands are environmental conditions requiring effort on the part of the student to mobilize and manage requisite resources. When the student is unable to do, so stress occurs. Stress thus refers to a condition of perceived tension between demands and resources during student life. When the student feels that he/she cannot meet the demands thrust on him/her, then he/she is stressed. Stress is inevitable in the life of a student. A major anxiety that is affecting them is how to achieve balance in life.

Adolescence begins with the onset of physiologically normal puberty, and ends when an adult identity and behavior are accepted. This period of development corresponds roughly to the period between the ages of 10 and 19 years, which is consistent with the World Health Organization's definition of adolescence. Due to fast physical changes and mental development at this stage, students may sometimes experience incompatibility of their mental development with their physical changes or with the social environment and thus suffer from problems arising from inadequate adaptations. These problems may further cause psychological troubles and even induce deviant behaviours.

2. Review of Literature:

Shauna L. Shapiro, M. A. Daniel E. Shapiro, and Gary E. R Schwartz (2000) conducted a study on 'stress management in medical Education: A review of literature'. The objective of this study was to review systematically clinical studies providing empirical data on stress management programs in medical training. The study reveals that medical trainees participating in stress management programs demonstrated improved immunological functioning, decrease in depression and anxiety, increased spirituality and empathy, enhanced knowledge of alternative therapies for future referrals and greater use of positive coping skills and the ability to resolve role conflicts. Emily. A. Pierceall and Marybelle C. Keim (2007) carried out a study entitled 'Stress and coping strategies among community college students'. The purpose of this study was to determine the degree of stress perceived by students at two community colleges in Southern Illinois. This study reveals that women

students were stressed than men; there were no statistically significant differences between traditional and non-traditional students. The most often used activities to cope with stress included to talk with family and friends, Leisure activities and exercising. Uma Devi. T (2011) carried out a study entitled “stress management and coping strategies with reference to IT companies”. The objectives of this study were to study the level of stress among IT employees and to identify stress coping strategies at organisational level. This study found some measures to reduce the impact of stress like self-exploration, character strength, leadership etc. Sue Hui Sun, Aziz Zorah (2015) were conducted a study on “Assessing stress among undergraduate pharmacy students in University of Malaya”. This study examined stress level and predictors of stress among pharmacy undergraduate students. This study reveals that the major source of perceived stress in the student population studied academic- related stress. While other variables were related to perceived stress academic factors are, to a degree, under the control of the university and it may be possible to vary these to the benefit of student stress levels.

The result of various studies which have been conducted over the years reveals that they concentrated a specific stress areas like academic or job related stress and more over no one has made attempt to find out the factors that influence a human mind especially among students as they are the next generation human resources. No one study made an attempt to assess the level of stress of graduates in general. Moreover these types of studies are not conducted in South India. So to fill this research gap this present study made an attempt to find out the causes for stress among graduates and create a powerful and stress free society for our better future.

3. Objectives of the Study:

This study carried out with the following objectives:

- ✓ To measure the level of stress among graduates.
- ✓ To find out the determinants that influence stress.
- ✓ To suggest stress management techniques to the students for maintaining or for reducing the level of stress.

4. Sampling:

In total 350 questionnaires were distributed among graduates. The questionnaire was divided in to three sections, socio-economic profile, questions for identifying the stress level and stress management techniques when they are in stress. Out of 350, 310 questionnaires were collected from the students, 15 questionnaires are found not suitable for analysis due to lack of information. Hence this study used the data of 295 graduates.

5. Frame Work of Analysis:

To test whether significant difference exists between Socio-Economic profile, stress management techniques and stress level of graduates, ANOVA has been applied. In order to find the association between Socio-Economic variables, stress management techniques and stress level Chi-square test has been applied. The total score of each student converted in to stress level index. The overall average stress index is 65.16. Of the total graduates the stress level of 151(71.90%) is above average and the rest 144 (65.16%) is below average. The stress level index ranges between 43.06 – 90.28.

6. Significance of the Study:

The findings of the study are useful to the students ,parents,teachers, edcational institutions and the Government.As the result reveals the stress level of students in the present atmosphere, it help the parents and teachers to take proper measures to relax them.In case of students they can identify the reason and symptoms of stress and can apply proper stress management technique by themselves.The findings of the study also useful to the educational institutions like college to adopt different stress management strategies and technique for the development of the whole organisation.It helps the Government to identify the existing condition of the youth and also it may useful to take necessary steps to regulate and frame new rules for the enhancement of the next generation.

7. Findings:

It could be inferred from table 1 that, the stress level of graduates who are classified on the basis of age. Between two groups, the average stress level index of graduates whose age is up to 21 years is 65.29. Their stress level ranges between 43.06 and 90.28.The average stress level of graduates whose age is 22 and above is 64.24.Their stress level ranges from 48.61 to 80.56.Between two groups, the stress level index is high with the graduates whose age group is up to 21.The average stress level of male students is 64.20.Out of 86 male graduates, their stress level index ranges between 43.06 and 90.28. The average stress level of female students is 65.56. Their stress level index ranges between 47.22 to 86.11.Among gender wise classification, the stress level is high among female graduates than compared to male graduates. The average stress level index of graduates in UG level is 64.52. Their stress level ranges from 43.06 to 90.28.The average stress level of graduates in PG and Research programme is 66.82. Their stress level ranges from 48.61 to 84.72.Between two groups, the stress level index is high with the students in PG level. The stress level of graduates who are classified on the basis of their family type. Between two groups, the average stress level index of graduates those who are coming from nuclear family is 65.60. Their stress level ranges from 47.22 to 86.11.The average

stress level of graduates those who are coming from joint family is 63.39. Their stress level ranges from 43.06 to 90.28. Between two groups, the stress level index is high with the graduates those who are coming from nuclear family.

The stress level of graduates who are classified on the basis of total family members. Between two groups, the average stress level index of graduates whose family members up to 4 is 65.37. Their stress level ranges from 47.22 to 88.89. The average stress level of graduates whose family members 5 and above is 64.51. Their stress level ranges from 43.06 to 90.28. Between two groups, the stress level index is high with the graduates whose total family members up to 4. The stress level of graduates who are classified on the basis of distance from residence to college. Between two groups, the average stress level index of graduates whose distance is up to 15 km from residence to college is 63.99. Their stress level ranges from 47.11 to 84.71. The average stress level of graduates whose distance is above 15 km is 66.16. Their stress level ranges from 43.06 to 90.28. Between two groups, the stress level index is high with the graduates whose distance is above 15 km. The stress level of graduates who are classified on the basis of parent's monthly income. Between three groups, the average stress level index of graduates whose parent's monthly income is less than 15000 is 65.40. Their stress level ranges from 43.06 to 88.89. The average stress level of graduates whose parent's monthly income is above 15000 is 64.81. Their stress level ranges from 48.61 to 84.72.

The stress level of graduates who are classified on the basis of the time for spirituality. Between two groups, the average stress level index of graduates who are spending time for spirituality daily is 65.37. Their stress level ranges from 43.06 to 90.28. The average stress level of graduate who are spending time for spirituality occasionally is 64.94. Their stress level ranges from 50.00 to 81.94. Between two groups, the stress level index is high with the graduates who are spending time for spirituality daily. The stress level of graduates who are classified on the basis of the time for outing with family or friends. Between two groups, the average stress level index of graduates who are spending time for outing frequently is 64.87. Their stress level ranges from 47.22 to 90.28.

The average stress level of graduate who are spending time for outing occasionally is 65.21. Their stress level ranges from 43.06 to 88.89. Between three groups, the average stress level index of graduates those who have the habit of reading books always when they are in stress is 62.70. Their stress level ranges from 47.22 to 86.11. The average stress level of graduates those who have the habit of reading books sometimes is 64.80. Their stress level ranges from 43.06 to 90.28. The stress level of graduates who are classified on the basis of the habit of using social Medias when they are in stress. Between three groups, the average stress level index of graduates those who have the habit of using social medias always when they are in stress is 66.73. Their stress level ranges from 43.06 to 90.28. The average stress level of graduates those who have the habit of using social medias sometimes is 64.72. Their stress level ranges from 47.22 to 84.72. The average stress level of graduates those who have not the habit of using social medias is 64.18. Their stress level ranges from 48.61 to 86.11. Between three groups, the stress level index is high with the graduates who have the habit of using social medias always.

The stress level of graduates who are classified on the basis of maintaining routine plan for each day. Between two groups, the average stress level index of graduates who are maintaining routine plan for each day is 64.82. Their stress level ranges from 43.06 to 90.28. The average stress level of graduates who are not maintaining routine plan for each day is 65.48. Their stress level ranges from 47.22 to 88.89. Between two groups, the stress level index is high with the graduates who are not maintaining routine plan for each day. The stress level of graduates who are classified on the basis of doing exercise or yoga. Between two groups, the average stress level index of graduates who are doing exercise or yoga daily is 62.72. Their stress level ranges between 43.06 and 90.28. The average stress level of graduates who are not doing exercise or yoga daily is 65.84. Their stress level ranges from 47.22 to 88.89. Between two groups, the stress level index is high with the graduates who are not doing exercise or yoga daily. The stress level of graduates who are classified on the basis of addiction to tea or coffee. Between two groups, the average stress level index of graduates who are addict to tea or coffee is 65.07. Their stress level ranges from 47.22 to 88.89. The average stress level of graduates who are not addict to tea or coffee is 65.22. Their stress level ranges from 43.06 to 90.28. There is not that much difference in stress level among graduates classified on the basis of addition to tea or coffee.

The stress level of graduates who are classified on the basis of work with enjoyment. Between two groups, the average stress level index of graduates who are doing the work always with enjoyment is 64.14. Their stress level ranges from 43.06 to 90.28. The average stress level of graduates who are not doing the work always with enjoyment is 66.35. Their stress level ranges from 47.22 to 86.11. Between two groups, the stress level index is high with the graduates who are not doing the work always with enjoyment. The stress level of graduates who are classified on the basis of getting good amount of rest and sleep at night. Between two groups, the average stress level index of graduates who are getting good amount of rest and sleep at night is 64.51. Their stress level ranges from 43.06 to 90.28. The average stress level of graduates who are not getting good amount of rest and sleep at night is 67.17. Their stress level ranges from 47.22 to 88.89. Between two groups, the stress level index is high with the graduates who are not getting good amount of rest and sleep at

night. The stress level of graduates who are classified on the basis of the habit of negative self-talk. Between two groups, the average stress level index of graduates who are having negative self-talk is 68.88. Their stress level ranges from 52.78 to 90.28. The average stress level of graduates who are not having negative self-talk is 63.11. Their stress level ranges from 43.06 to 81.94. Between two groups, the stress level index is high with the graduates who are having negative self-talk.

The stress level of graduates who are classified on the basis of the level of agreement about both working parents affect stress level. Between three groups, the average stress level index of graduates who agreeing that both working parents affect stress level is 65.82. Their stress level ranges from 47.22 to 86.11. The average stress level of graduates who are not agreeing that both working parents affect stress level is 65.32. Their stress level ranges from 43.06 to 90.28. The average stress level of graduates who are agreeing to some extent that both working parents affect stress level is 63.89. Their stress level ranges from 47.22 to 88.89. Between three groups, the stress level index is high with the graduates who are agreeing that both working parents affect stress level.

The stress level of graduates who are classified on the basis of the habit of discussing problems with others. Between three groups, the average stress level index of graduates those who have the habit of discussing problems always with others is 65.73. Their stress level ranges from 43.06 to 80.56. The average stress level of graduates those who have the habit of discussing problems with others sometimes is 65.16. Their stress level ranges from 47.22 to 90.28. The average stress level of graduates those who have not the habit of discussing problems with others is 60.15. Their stress level ranges from 50.00 to 75.00. Between three groups, the stress level index is high with the graduates who have the habit of discussing problems with others always. The stress level of graduates who are classified on the basis of the habit of analysing problems when they are in stress. Between three groups, the average stress level index of graduates those who have the habit of analysing problems always when they are in stress is 65.34. Their stress level ranges from 43.06 to 90.28. The average stress level of graduates those who have the habit of analysing problems sometimes is 64.66. Their stress level ranges from 47.22 to 88.89.

The stress level of graduates who are classified on the basis of the habit of listening to music when they are in stress. Between three groups, the average stress level index of graduates those who have the habit of listening to music always when they are in stress is 65.35. Their stress level ranges from 43.06 to 90.28. The average stress level of graduates those who have the habit of listening to music sometimes is 64.74. Their stress level ranges from 48.61 to 88.89. The average stress level of graduates those who have not the habit of listening to music is 63.73. Their stress level ranges from 52.78 to 75.00. Between three groups, the stress level index is high with the graduates who have the habit of listening to music always.

To test whether any significant difference exists among Socio-economic and stress management techniques ANOVA has been applied. In order to find the association between socio economic and stress management variables and the level of stress among graduates Chi-square test has been applied.

Table 1: Socio-Economic Profile and Stress management techniques adopted by Graduates

Factors	No. of Students & ASI (N=295)	F Value	Factors	No. of Students (N=295)	F Value
Age(years) Up to 21 22and above	259(65.29) 36(64.24)	0.4676	Maintaining a routine plan Maintaining Not maintaining	144(64.82) 151(65.48)	0.4226
Gender Male Female	86(64.20) 209(65.56)	1.5089	Doing exercise/yoga daily Doing Not doing	64(62.72) 231(65.84)	6.6394
Education level UG PGand Research programme	213(64.52) 82(66.82)	4.2184	Addict to tea or coffee Addicted Not addicted	119(65.07) 176(65.22)	0.0227
Family type Nuclear Joint	236(65.60) 59(63.39)	3.0938	Work with enjoyment Always Never	159(64.14) 136(66.35)	4.8324
Total family member Up to 4 5 and above	223(65.37) 72(64.51)	0.5430	Good rest and sleep Getting Not getting	223(64.51) 72(67.17)	5.2028
Distance level Up to 15 kms Above 15 kms	155(63.99) 140(66.16)	4.6482	Negative self-talk Doing Not doing	237(68.88) 58(63.11)	33.3692
Parent's monthly income Up to 15000 Above 15000	186(65.40) 109(64.81)	0.1908	Level of Agreement about working parents (both) affect stress level Agree Disagree To some extend	144(65.82) 68(65.32) 83(63.89)	1.3263

Time for spirituality Daily Occasionally	150(65.37) 145(64.94)	0.1796	Habit of discussing problems with others Always Some times Never	114(65.73) 168(65.16) 13(60.15)	2.4488
Time for outing Frequently Occasionally	44(64.87) 251(65.21)	0.0592	Analysing problems Always Some times Never	136(65.34) 140(64.66) 19(67.54)	0.9812
Habit of reading books Always Some times Never	34(62.7) 137(64.8) 124(66.12)	2.4591	Habit of listening to music Always Sometimes Never	219(65.35) 67(64.74) 9(63.73)	0.2518
Habit of using social Medias Always Some times Never	90(66.73) 110(64.72) 95(64.18)	2.2470	ASI-Average Stress Index Overall ASI=65.16 (Table value at 5% level)		

Table 1 reveals the result of ANOVA test that, there exists a significant difference in the stress level among graduate's educational level, distance from residence to college, doing exercise or yoga daily, doing work always with enjoyment, getting good amount of rest and sleep at night, and negative self-talk.

Table 2: Attributes associated with the stress level of graduates

Variables	$\sqrt{2}$	Variables	χ^2
Age	1.80	Routine plan daily	1.774
Gender	1.72	Exercise or Yoga daily	6.785*
Level of Education	12.13*	Addict to tea or coffee	1.889
Type of family	0.715	Doing work with enjoyment	8.199*
Total family members	0.185	Rest and sleep at night	5.790**
Distance from residence	5.764**	Negative self-talk	29.406*
Parents monthly income	0.446	Both working parents affect stress level	12.925*
Time for spirituality	2.932	Discussing problems with others	11.450*
Time for outing	3.284	Analysis problems	13.027*
Habit of reading books	11.868*	Listening to music	1.847
Using social medias	8.647	* Significant @5% level ** Significant @10 % level	

Table 2 exhibits the variables which are associated with the stress level of graduates. Chi-square test has been administered to find out the association between the selected variables and the level of stress. It is clear that the level of education, distance from residence to college, reading habit, exercise or yoga daily, doing work with enjoyment, rest and sleep at night, habit of negative self-talk, both working parents, discussing problems with friends and analysis of problems are associated with the stress level of graduates.

8. Suggestions:

- ✓ **To the Students:** Students should do exercise or yoga daily and should ensure that they are getting proper rest and sleep at night and should try to do the work with enjoyment. They should avoid negative self-talk by practicing some mind relaxing techniques like meditation, breathing exercise etc. and should talk their problems with their friends and relatives those who have a positive or an optimistic mind. Students should have a habit of reading some motivational books to relax their mind.
- ✓ **To the Parents:** Parents should create a positive environment at home and should motivate their children to do the work with enjoyment. They should take initiative to make an arrangement to do the exercise or yoga at home and should communicate friendly with their children to boost their confidence. Parents should take initiative for motivating the reading habit of their children and should ensure that children are getting good amount of rest and sleep at night. They should take the children out and to show the values of life by visiting the orphanage, hospitals, old age homes etc. Parents should be the role model to their children for happy and stress free life.
- ✓ **To the Teachers:** Teachers should provide necessary arrangements for improving their student's personality inside and outside the class room and should take initiative to arrange some motivational classes for their students (at least once in a month).. Teachers should compel the students to do exercise or yoga daily and should be the role model to the students. They should give some work to their students for using the library in a fruitful way and should keep a smile on their face always as it will influence their students a lot and it will create a positive environment among students.
- ✓ **To the Educational Institution:** The educational institution should provide necessary arrangements to develop their students mentally and physically and should provide some motivational programs to the parents and teachers regularly. The educational institution should provide necessary arrangements for the transportation facility for their students.

- ✓ **To the Government:** The Government has to make the education policy by keeping the physical and mental health of students and should conduct some orientation and motivational programs for the teachers and students at regular intervals.

9. Conclusion:

Stress management is not an easy work among students. Students should face the stress and should plan for managing it in a proper manner. But it is not possible by telling simple words as a sound and positive environment should be there among students. A good and proper guidance should be followed by the students. Many factors from the family, from the educational institution and from the society which influence the students a lot. In order to overcome all the barrier which are against to the development of the students should identify and proper measures should be taken.

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